

1 **Innovation in the use of wood energy in the Ukrainian Carpathians:**
2 **Opportunities and threats for rural communities**

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17

18 **Abstract**

19 Ukraine is traditionally deeply dependent on fossil and nuclear energy. However, in response to global
20 climate and energy policies, a major shift towards renewable energy (RE) is presently underway. Apart
21 from ample wind and solar capacities, the country has abundant bioenergy resources, mainly from
22 agriculture and forestry. Particularly in the densely-forested Ukrainian Carpathians, wood is the most
23 prominent bioenergy source used to meet the heat demands of households and public buildings.
24 However, despite increasing forest area and timber volume in this region during the last 50 years,
25 affordable bioenergy from forests remains scarce in many areas. At the same time, local communities
26 suffer from energy scarcity, energy insecurity and high energy costs.

27 In an effort to understand how better use might be made of Ukraine's bioenergy resource, addressing
28 sustainability goals as well as the needs of local communities, this study assesses the significance and
29 future potential of wood energy for regional economies and households from an environmental,
30 economic and social perspective. The study employs a mixed-method approach combining literature
31 review, a Best Practice contest and semi-structured interviews with forestry sector stakeholders in
32 rural areas of Transcarpathia and Lviv. Several reasons were identified for the scarcity of affordable
33 bioenergy, including the export-oriented wood processing industry, the lack of forest road networks
34 and machinery, the short-term character of national forest strategies in relation to bioenergy, and
35 other institutional settings that limit access to forest resources. Illegal logging, corruption, and laxck of
36 transparency in -and corrupt and non-transparent timber markets add further difficulties. To address
37 these problems and to meet the challenges defined by international climate agreements, two key
38 innovative instruments were identified; 1) certification schemes for forest products and; 2)
39 community-driven bioenergy initiatives (e.g. local cooperatives.). These approaches, ideally embedded
40 in a local energy strategy developed by the communities themselves, have the potential to transform
41 energy and benefit communities and the local economy.

42 **Keywords:** Energy transition, community-based pilot projects, domestic renewable energy, fuel wood,
43 certification schemes, social innovation

44 **Highlights**

- 45
- 46 • Households in rural Ukraine suffer energy insecurity and fuel poverty despite the fact that
47 bioenergy from forests is ample and widely locally available.
 - 48 • To enhance energy security in rural areas of Ukraine, institutional and regulatory settings need
49 to be improved at the governmental level, while carefully structured participatory processes and
50 social innovation are required at the local level, e.g. in form of Civil Society Organisations or
51 Energy Cooperatives.
 - 52 • Wood certification schemes applied and adapted to the provision of fuel wood could be an
53 appropriate measure to boost the energy transition, to enhance energy security and to generate
54 income for rural communities.
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55 1. Introduction

56 Although the energy transition is a key challenge for the entire global community (EU Commission
57 2014; WEF 2017), options and specific transition pathways need to be identified, negotiated and
58 decided on at the national level. The internationally adopted climate objectives negotiated under the
59 Paris agreement and the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (UN 2015), for instance, imply
60 a significant expansion of renewable energies (REs) worldwide. Bioenergy, the focus of this paper,
61 accounts for about 10 % of the world's primary energy consumption, yet its potential could be
62 increased to about 15 % of the world's energy demand by 2035 (IEA 2016).

63 Transforming Ukraine's energy sector is essential to strengthening the country's economic and
64 national security. Despite having ample domestic energy resources, these cover only half of the
65 country's energy demand. Currently Ukraine generates more than 50% of its electricity from outdated
66 coal and nuclear power plants, several of which already operate beyond their designed lifetime.
67 Hydropower and other renewables contribute a negligible share (Savitsky 2016). In the recent past,
68 the energy situation became even more critical. The country's dependence on Russia for nuclear fuels
69 and the suspension of domestic coal supply for thermal power plants from Donetsk and Luhansk
70 regions as a result of the armed conflict in Eastern Ukraine, make the task of energy transition
71 especially urgent (Yurkovich 2018). Furthermore, old and inefficient technologies mean that the
72 country is one of the world's most energy intensive economies (Kholod et al 2018). Together with
73 fostering RE production, increasing energy efficiency is therefore an important goal.

74 The Ukrainian Government aims to strongly promote green energy by adopting the Energy Strategy of
75 Ukraine and the draft National Renewable Energy Action Plan prepared by the State Agency on Energy
76 Efficiency and Energy Saving of Ukraine (SAEE). The latter is intended to define a pathway towards the
77 target of 11% electricity from renewables by the year 2020 (Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine 2014), and
78 25% by 2035 (Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine 2017). In terms of total energy, the share of REs remains
79 small (about 6% in 2014 (State Statistics Service of Ukraine 2016), however, it is projected to increase
80 to 20% by 2030 (Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine 2017). To attract investment for renewable electricity
81 production, Ukraine has set a green tariff system at 6 to 17 cents/kWh under a guaranteed purchase
82 arrangement until 2030. Such incentives are crucial for the development of REs in the country
83 (Trypolska 2012). While it is no longer mandatory for production of REs to include a local component
84 (e.g. equipment produced in Ukraine) in order to obtain green tariffs, power plants that do so are
85 rewarded with extra bonuses (Janda et al. 2017).

86 Recently, the Ukrainian Parliament supported a number of bills aimed at the development of green
87 energy in 2019 and the maintenance of favourable conditions for its development in 2020. In addition,
88 from 2020, a new mechanism for state support of producers of electricity from alternative sources, in
89 the form of price auctions, will be introduced. The starting price will be the "green" tariff, valid at the
90 time the auction is conducted. While some of these laws are still awaiting final parliamentary approval,
91 the fact that they are under consideration is a clear sign of progress towards "greening" the Ukrainian
92 economy.

93 Alongside other REs, bioenergy could contribute 4.6% to the primary energy consumption by 2030
94 (Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine 2017). The total biomass potential is estimated to 21.2 Mio. t of oil
95 equivalent per year (2016). With 2.6 Mio. t oil equivalent per year, the share of bioenergy from wood
96 is relatively small in national terms; the share of bioenergy from agricultural waste and by-products is
97 much larger. However, in the Ukrainian Carpathians, where forest cover reaches almost 50%, wood as
98 an energy source has a considerable potential.

99 **1.1 Aims and objectives**

100 This paper investigates opportunities and threats arising from the anticipated increase of wood fuel
101 use in forest-dependent regions of the Ukrainian Carpathians. It focusses on the importance of
102 innovative bottom-up RE initiatives in these regions, as a means of increasing energy security and
103 enhancing the socio-economic development and resilience of local communities.

104 This research was conducted under the remit of the Swiss-Ukrainian project "Identifying Green Energy
105 Options for the Ukrainian Carpathians" (2017-2020) led by the Swiss Federal Research Institute WSL in
106 partnership with the Ukrainian National Forestry University, the NGO Agency of sustainable
107 development of the Carpathian region FORZA, and the Center for Development and Environment (CDE)
108 of the University of Bern. The project emphasized the importance of societally relevant research (cf.
109 Pohl et al. 2017), and co-production of knowledge with stakeholders from forest-dependent
110 communities in the regions Transcarpathia and Lviv was a key element of the work.

111 Our research addressed four questions:

- 112 - What is the potential for sustainable energy from forest wood in the Ukrainian Carpathians?
- 113 - What innovative RE initiatives are currently implemented in these regions?
- 114 - What kinds of social innovations in the field of REs could promote local development at a larger
115 scale?
- 116 - Could forest certification schemes be expanded to include fuel wood in order to promote the
117 sustainable use of wood energy in the Ukrainian Carpathians?

118

119 **1.2 Study area**

120 Although the Ukrainian Carpathians cover only around 4% of Ukraine's territory, they produce one
121 third of its forest resources (Nijnik et al. 2009; Melnykovich et al. 2018). The Carpathian region consists
122 of four administrative units: Transcarpathia, Lviv, Ivano-Frankivsk, and Chernivtsi (Fig. 1). Forests
123 occupy almost 42% of the territory and play an important role in the livelihoods of forest-dependent
124 communities (Melnykovich et al. 2018; Melnykovich and Soloviy 2014). Forest income contributes
125 around 5% of total household incomes in forested regions of the Carpathians. According to the ENPI
126 FLEG II Program (2016) collection of non-timber forest products, including resins, Christmas trees, wild
127 fruits and berries, and birch sap, is an important activity of the local population. Forestry is a profitable
128 economic activity in the region. The forestry sector plays an important role, particularly in rural areas
129 where unemployment is high, in terms of provision of jobs and maintenance of rural communities,
130 while also providing essential environmental services (seen also in Forestry 2006; ENPI FLEG II Program
131 2016). Yet, due to the state monopoly on timber harvesting, many communities do not benefit from
132 the profits of these activities (Nijnik et al. 2012; Sarkki et al. 2019). Communities receive only small
133 shares of the revenues paid by forestry enterprises in the form of stumpage fees. The contribution of
134 such payments to local budgets in 2017 was nearly UAH 1 billion, while the total amount of taxes on
135 forestry enterprises in 2017 was about 4 billion UAH (Bondar 2018).

136
 137 **Fig. 1** Land cover in the Ukrainian Carpathians. Lviv and Uzhgorod are the main cities of the two case
 138 studies located in the administrative regions (oblasts) of Lviv and Transcarpathia (*Map by Anatoliy*
 139 *Smaliychuk, Ivan Franko National University, Lviv*).

140 In contrast to the steady increase in forest area and volume in Ukraine during the last 50 years,
 141 affordable bioenergy from forests is scarce. Unlike in the rest of Ukraine, wood is the most prominent
 142 bioenergy source in the Carpathians and is widely used for heating in households and public buildings.
 143 Wood is still collected and used for fuel in large quantities due to the high price of gas (Bakkegaard
 144 2014; ENPI-FLEG II 2016). Thus, in the absence of alternatives, wood still remains the main source for
 145 heating and cooking in most forest-dependent communities in the Carpathians and as such, is essential
 146 during winter months, in particular in remote areas (Bakkegaard 2014; Melnykovich et al 2018).
 147 According to Chernyavskyy et al. (2011), a typical household needs from 6 to 12 m³ of fuel wood for
 148 heating, depending on the household size and its insulation, and the quality of the wood (e.g., tree
 149 species).

150 **2. Materials and methods**

151 **2.1 Methods**

152 The research followed a mixed-method approach (Morse 2016) comprising three distinct phases.

153 In Phase 1, a comprehensive understanding of the energy wood potential and fuel wood consumption
 154 in the Ukrainian Carpathians was acquired through literature analysis.

155 To identify initiatives and best practices in the region, to establish contacts to local actors and to learn
156 about opportunities and obstacles related to wood energy use at the local level, a Best Practice Contest
157 was launched in early 2018 (Phase 2). It addressed individuals, households, legal entities, public
158 institutions and communities. The entry form asked for the description of the energy challenges in the
159 locality where the practice has been implemented, what has been done and how it contributed to
160 solving the problem of energy dependency on external sources. It also asked for target groups that had
161 benefited from the practice or activity, and the overall implementation costs. The contest considered
162 both examples of practices already implemented as well as those that had not yet been carried out.
163 Proposals had to be related to the use of woody biomass (timber, firewood, chips, sawdust, pellets,
164 briquettes) for heat or electricity production, or to efficiency measures.

165 Proposals were assessed by an international evaluation committee on the basis of: 1) *thematic*
166 *relevance* (the contribution of the activities to higher energy independence, e.g. by better resource
167 allocation or more efficient use of woody biomass); 2) *effectiveness (including cost-effectiveness),*
168 *efficiency and transferability* to other places; and 3) the *impact and sustainability* (long-term impact
169 on the target groups, use of local resources, support of local people). Submissions had to contain a
170 clear proposal on how the innovation grant, i.e. the prize money for the winners, was to be invested.

171 In summer 2018, five winners were awarded innovation grants of between 700 and 1300 CHF. The
172 grants were intended to further improve energy use and efficiency measures the winners had
173 proposed (e.g. devices or equipment). The 14 proposals submitted to the Best Practice Contest
174 provided valuable material for the subsequent analysis of innovative pathways in using wood for
175 energy in the study region while taking advantage of locally available expertise, experience and ideas.

176 In Phase 3, 61 semi-structured interviews were carried out with forest business-associated
177 stakeholders on the subject of innovative bioenergy products certification initiatives. The survey was
178 targeted at forestry and wood processing enterprises producing pellets, briquettes, or charcoal. It
179 aimed to understand the attitude of managers responsible for certification, together with other
180 aspects of certification for wood biofuels. The hypothesis of the study was that bioenergy certification
181 would facilitate the emergence of a market for certified bioenergy products based on an emerging
182 network of enterprises and consumers, which can be understood as a form of social innovation.

183 3. Results

184 3.1 Ukraine's forest bioenergy potential

185 Solid biofuels such as firewood, wood chips, biomass pellets and briquettes occupy the biggest part of
186 biofuel market. The total production of pellets in Ukraine in 2015 was about 1.32 Mt produced by 494
187 plants, including up to 390 kt of wood pellets (Geletukha et al. 2018). According to the State Statistics
188 Committee of Ukraine, in January 2019, Ukraine exported 126.4 thousand tons (including 80.4
189 thousand tons to Europe) of wood fuel in the form of logs, brushwood, branches, knots, wood chips;
190 sawdust, wood chips, shavings, and waste wood and scrap, briquettes, granules, etc. worth 114.9
191 million USD.

192 Across the Ukrainian Carpathians, the available fuel wood resources are often not sufficient to meet
193 the energy demands of rural households. As many villages do not have natural gas supply, households
194 fully rely on fuel wood for heating. Even if they have a grid connection, poor households may simply
195 not be able to afford to switch to gas. As a result, fuel wood remains essential in remote rural mountain
196 areas, as is the case in Transcarpathia, where firewood is the major fuel for heating and cooking in

197 rural and remote forested areas (Melnykovich et al. 2018). Private users have legal and free access
 198 only to thin branches of less than 3 cm diameter. Bigger logs can be purchased from local forestry
 199 enterprises or wood processing enterprises. In practice, fuel wood is cut illegally (Melnykovich and
 200 Soloviy 2014) therefore remaining unreported. Increased wood prices make households look for
 201 cheaper alternatives such as wood chips or lumber waste supplied by numerous wood processing
 202 enterprises in the region. This situation has led to increased competition between industry and
 203 households for wood biomass.

204 Unlike in other countries, wood is still a major source of bioenergy in the Ukrainian Carpathians (FORZA
 205 2017). With 355 t oil equivalent, the estimated potential in the Ukrainian Carpathians is about one
 206 fourth of the total country. In fact, all four mountain regions produce considerable amounts of wood
 207 processing residuals (Table 1).

208 **Table 1.** Estimated technical sustainable energy potential of woody biomass (in t oil equ.) in the
 209 Ukrainian Carpathians for 2013 (based on S2Biom Report 2016)

	Harvesting residuals		Wood-processing residuals		Firewood		Woody biomass. total	
	t oil equ.	%	t oil equ.	%	t oil equ.	%	t oil equ.	%
Transcarpathia	17.9	7%	6	3%	68.7	8%	92.6	7%
Ivano-Frankivsk	16.7	6%	28.9	14%	37.2	4%	82.8	6%
Lviv	19.1	7%	16.5	8%	67.5	8%	103	7%
Chernivtsi	14.3	5%	4.7	2%	58.1	6%	77	6%
Ukrainian Carpathians, total	68	25%	56.1	27%	231.5	26%	355.4	26%
Ukraine, total	271	100%	209	100%	898	100%	1378	100%

211
 212 State forest enterprises supply timber, but no harvesting residues or wood chips due to the lack of
 213 wood chippers. Forest legislation neither regulates the use of harvesting residues for energy
 214 production nor provides appropriate access to private enterprises to make use of wood residues. In
 215 any case, collecting and transporting harvesting residues is not profitable for state forest enterprises.
 216 As a result, wood chips are mostly supplied to consumers by private entrepreneurs.

217 Geletukha et al. (2018) estimated that the current volume of solid biofuel production (wood pulp)
 218 amounts to only 17% of the technically achievable potential of 30 Mio. t/year, providing an immense
 219 potential for improvement. Apart from the advantages in terms of the energy it would provide, a more
 220 efficient utilization of wood residues throughout the processing chain could generate additional
 221 revenues for forestry companies, while reducing their environmental impact and generating new
 222 opportunities for forest-dependent communities. To optimize forest-based processing facilities, a
 223 whole set of conditions had to be met, related to biomass procurement, logistics, technologies, and
 224 sustainability (Camberoa and Sowlatib 2016). In order to address current and future trade-offs and to
 225 tap the full potential of synergies related to other forest ecosystem services, it is important that forest
 226 management and related policies take into account possible impacts of energy wood production and
 227 trade (Peters et al. 2015).

228 Wood and wood residues (80%, Table 2) currently represent the biggest share of annual bioenergy
 229 consumption in Ukraine, although the area of forest cover in Ukraine is relatively small (17%). The
 230 estimated annual volumes of wood wastes for further processing into biomass include 1.4 Mio. m³ of
 231 felling residues, 1.1 Mio. m³ of wood processing waste, and 3.8 Mio. m³ of firewood (Geletukha et al.
 232 2006; 2012).

233 **Table 2.** Biomass and biofuel utilization for energy production in Ukraine. Source: Lakyda et al. 2011

Type of biomass/biofuel	Annual consumption (kt oil equ.)	Current usage of economic potential, %
Straw from grain and rapeseed	43	1
Biomass from wood	1296	80
Sunflower husk	343	42
Bioethanol	53.6	70
Biodiesel	0	0

234 The forest biomass potential is obviously concentrated in highly forested regions: about 35% of all
 235 forest biomass for energy purposes is concentrated in Polissia (plain forest zone, north west Ukraine),
 236 30% in the Carpathians and in the forest-steppe zone, and 5% in the steppe zone of Ukraine (Lakyda
 237 et al. 2011). From an economic point of view, most of the favourable energy biomass resources are
 238 concentrated in the Carpathian region (Lopatin et al. 2011).

239 A recent project study (Vorobei and Hudz 2017) identified the following barriers hampering the
 240 development of a forest bioenergy market in Ukraine (sorted in order of importance):

- 241 a. Lacking motivation of state forest enterprises;
- 242 b. Low density of forest roads;
- 243 c. The lack of specialized equipment, which means that harvesting of secondary raw materials
 244 for energy purposes must take place on the road; and
- 245 d. Low biomass market prices leading to low profitability.

246 Geletukha et al. (2018) added other obstacles, such as:

- 247 e. Complicated processes to provide private companies access to logging residues (e.g. for
 248 energy use);
- 249 f. Absence of record keeping for the logging residues; and
- 250 g. Absence of plans for the permanent use of forest for solid wood fuel harvesting under
 251 national strategic plans.

252 Provided that these barriers can be overcome, forest biofuel could significantly contribute to the
 253 energy transition, especially in the highly forested Carpathian regions (Lakyda et al. 2011). The better
 254 use of wood fuel could benefit both the local economy and the socio-ecological system as a whole.

255 Furthermore, according to the latest report by the European Court of Auditors, the links between the
 256 production and use of renewable (wood) energy and rural local development across Europe should be
 257 reinforced (ECA 2018). REs projects could benefit local communities, linking REs and local development
 258 policies and tools. Although large energy companies still dominate the generation and supply of energy
 259 across Europe, recent years have seen a notable increase in locally-driven energy initiatives, so-called
 260 *community energy* (Hewitt et al. 2019), in which communities of various kinds are becoming

261 increasingly involved in the generation, supply and management of sustainable energy (Oteman et al.
262 2014).

263 3.2 Best Practice Contest for wood fuel usage in the Ukrainian Carpathians

264 The 14 proposals submitted to the Best Practice Contest represented six businesses, five communities,
265 and three households in the Lviv and Transcarpathia regions. Five proposals dealt with energy
266 plantations, seven with heat production and two with the improvement of cooperation opportunities
267 related to REs. Most proposals addressed the improvement of continuous biomass supply (e.g.
268 mobilization of woody biomass, substitution of woody biomass with agricultural biomass) or technical
269 aspects (e.g. conversation of gas to solid biomass boilers, insulation, or energy efficiency measures).
270 Innovation in this context is understood as technical modernization and change in response to local
271 priorities. Table 3 shows the five best-practice cases from the contest that rated highest in terms of
272 applicability and potential for replication.

273 **Table 3:** Best-practice cases awarded in the frame of the Best Practice Contest in 2018

Name of practice	Description	Project Initiator	Innovative aspects
Biomass boiler installation	Installation of a 100 KW biomass heating system replacing the old gas heating system	School No 9, Boryslav	The school organized its own sourcing of fuel. Procurement contracts are negotiated with the Drohobych state forest enterprise, the city forestry or local sawmills.
Growing willow for energy in private garden	Willow biomass production for domestic (private) heat supply. 10,000 <i>Salix viminalis</i> saplings planted on private 0.5 ha plot	Private household in town of Zhydachiv	Use of the fast-growing energy plants for private household heat supply to reduce energy costs.
District heating with woody biomass	The town shifts from gas to woody biomass. Four gas boilers were reequipped with solid fuel combustion appliances. Heat networks were newly insulated.	Zhovkva town council & Zhovkateploenergo communal company	The city conducted a "biomass logistic study" in 2017 to optimize local woody biomass supply and consumption. This approach has a high potential to influence regional policy.
Energy saving technologies and efficiency measures in kindergarten	With public and international funding, the heating system of the kindergarten was replaced and combined with a modular boiler-house.	Velykyy Bereznyy town council	The kindergarten can now use both firewood and pellets, making fuel supply more flexible and cost effective. The town plans own pellet production for self-supply.

Full utilization of sawmill and wood processing residues by wood processing company	The company is located in a region that is not connected to the gas grid. A joint effort of local authorities and the wood-based industry aims at a reliable and affordable energy supply.	VGSM Ltd based in Velykyy Bychkiv, Rakhiv district	Small sawmills in the area annually generate 30'000 m3 of sawdust that is only partially burned or recycled, the rest is dumped. VGSM wants to establish a collection and cleaning system to use sawdust either for heating or briquettes production.
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274 The Best Practice Contest was meant to identify, support and disseminate ideas, practices and
275 innovations in the field of energy wood. It facilitated the dialogue among participants, e.g. during the
276 public award ceremony and site visits, thereby encouraging them to reassess their ideas and to make
277 use of cooperation opportunities or innovative business models.

278 The best practices identified all show potential for extension to other rural or urban communities in
279 the Ukrainian Carpathians facing similar challenges (e.g. inhabitants, foresters, entrepreneurs, mayors,
280 and teachers). Making the ideas available online can encourage others to take steps to improve their
281 energy situation with similar small-scale initiatives or through cooperation.

282 3.3 Bioenergy certification for forestry-related businesses

283 FSC-certified forests in Ukraine cover 4,28 Mio. ha or 41% of the forest area of the country. The FSC
284 certification bodies has issued 108 Forest Management/Chain of Custody (FM/CoC) certificates to the
285 forest management enterprises and 256 chain of custody (CoC) certificates to the wood processing
286 organizations and traders (FSC, 2019). The Bioenergy Association of Ukraine (UABio) appealed to the
287 National FSC office about the negative environmental impact of burning harvesting residues directly
288 at logging plots instead of using them for bioenergy production. Also UABio proposed to introduce a
289 criterion (indicator) into the FSC certification forest management standard in Ukraine that should take
290 into account the share of logging residues use as secondary raw materials (UABio, 2018). In the
291 meantime, interest in other certification schemes focused on different aspects or sustainability of
292 biomass production for energy purpose is increasing.

293 The semi-structured interviews showed that fuel wood certification schemes could potentially be
294 implemented in the Ukrainian context. However, it is unclear how customers would perceive such
295 certification schemes, as they entail higher fuel wood prices. In line with our original hypothesis, 75%
296 of the respondents (n=61) felt that the implementation of fuel wood certification schemes would lead
297 to the development of new markets. 88% of the respondents were convinced that certification
298 schemes would yield benefits from the bioenergy products. 41% stated that certification would help
299 to enter international markets and could consolidate their positions there, while 14 (23%) believed
300 that certification would enhance their company's image and build the trust of customers (15
301 respondents; 24%) (Fig. 2a). Interestingly, only 22 (36%) were aware of bio-energy certification
302 schemes such as DINplus, SBP, REDcert, which are currently entering the wood products certification
303 market in Ukraine.

304 27% of the interviewees identified the lack of motivation from enterprises as the main barriers to
305 bioenergy products certification in Ukraine, 18% judged the high cost of the certification process as
306 an obstacle (Fig. 2b).

Fig. 2a Expected *benefits* arising from bioenergy product certification in the Ukrainian Carpathians (n= 61)

Fig. 2b Expected *barriers* for bioenergy products certification in the Ukrainian Carpathians (n= 61)

307 The survey results have shown that more than half the respondents (33) view embedding the
 308 certification costs in the product production costs as the best option. 40 respondents (66%) agreed
 309 that increasing the price of certified products would be acceptable, but differed markedly in the
 310 percentage price increase they felt to be appropriate (not greater than 10%, 11 (18%); up to 20% - 15
 311 (25%); up to 40% - 12 (20%); up to 50 % - 2 (3%). Some interviewees believed that the price increase
 312 should be minimal or absent to keep competitive affordable prices.

313 Interviews show that stakeholders view certification of wood fuel in Ukraine as appropriate and
 314 feasible, as it generates opportunities/benefits in terms of market development for wood fuel, CO₂
 315 reduction, and enhanced energy independence. The certification would increase consumer
 316 confidence, guarantee product quality and stimulate environmental protection. Moving in this
 317 direction is, however, hampered by the fact that producers, enterprises and consumers lack knowledge
 318 about certification schemes. So far, most enterprises sell products in markets where certification is not
 319 a main criterion for choosing a certain product. Some wood fuel businesses in Ukraine, however,
 320 already serve export markets with certified products. From the available certification instruments, the
 321 FSC scheme attracted most attention. Certified businesses are found likely to access new markets and
 322 customers (Fig. 3a).

323 On the demand side, most respondents believe that certification schemes serve as a quality label for
 324 customers (Fig. 3b). Half the interviewees believe that such certification would benefit communities
 325 though environmental protection. Other advantages are the product quality guarantee, the legality
 326 of the origin of wood and better image of the enterprise (Fig. 3c).

327

- Company image
- Number of consumers increase
- Product origin
- Quality of the product
- Consumers' trust
- Guarantee of the product legality

Fig. 3a. Companies' expected benefits from bioenergy product certification (wood fuel)

- Product quality
- Environmental features of the product
- Legality of the product origin
- Conformance of the product characteristics

Fig. 3b. Consumers' expected benefits from bioenergy product certification (wood fuel)

- Minimized environmental impact
- Legality of the product
- Environmental features of the product
- Product quality

Fig. 3c. Society's expected benefits from bioenergy product certification (wood fuel)

328

329 Bioenergy certification schemes do not cover all sustainability concerns, but may help to improve
330 decision-making by providing more sophisticated analyses.

331 **4 Discussion**

332 Various factors have led to a delay in Ukraine's energy transition process. The high degree of
333 uncertainty in the legal and regulatory environment is one crucial factor; others include lack of
334 regulatory and procedural transparency regarding land acquisition, planning approval, grid connection,
335 and off-take agreements. Moreover, commercial funding for renewable energy (REs) projects is limited
336 and domestic financial institutions are not trained to assess these projects and their related risks. On
337 the other hand, domestic project developers are not experienced in the field of REs. All these factors
338 hamper the development of strong project proposals and lead to a distorted view of the viability of
339 REs investments (Buchan and Keay 2016). Potential negative environmental impacts arising, should
340 forest bioenergy be developed without sustainable management regimes, include reduced soil fertility
341 and soil erosion. Also, over-intensive clearing of forest felling areas for biomass collection can lead to
342 carbon release and biodiversity losses.

343 However, these difficulties are not unique to Ukraine but represent a challenge for many economies.
344 The fact that Ukraine officially joined the International Renewable Energy Agency (IRENA) in February
345 2018 will stimulate learning from international experiences in energy transition. It is clear that the
346 energy transition in Ukraine will require profound structural changes in its administration, as well as
347 transformations at local and regional levels. A particular threat may be the overexploitation of
348 resources by local communities and forest-related businesses once resources become accessible and

349 profitable. A study commissioned by Earthsight showed how indiscriminate and illegal sanitary felling
350 in protected forests had been occurring all over Ukraine. Illegal sanitary harvesting was discovered in
351 fifteen National Parks, including the Carpathian Biosphere Reserve (Earthsight 2018). The promotion
352 of certification schemes for energy wood would no doubt be an appropriate measure, yet should not
353 be mistaken as a panacea, as it again bears the risk of misuse. Last but not least, sensitive engagement
354 with local communities is required to prevent conflicts over the use and sovereignty of forest
355 resources.

356 **4.1 Stakeholders' attitudes towards green energy projects**

357 Community initiatives for REs are emerging across Europe (Hewitt et al 2019). They vary in size, success
358 rates and in their strategies. Decentralization appears to be one of the most important characteristics
359 of the general institutional development and generally increases the institutional space for local
360 players (Oteman et al. 2014). This can also be observed in Ukraine with a growing number of initiatives
361 led by communities, civil societies and NGOs, or those promoted at different levels of the government
362 (Buchan and Keay 2016).

363 Despite the positive spirit of change, literature review reveals that systemic problems hamper the rapid
364 development and diffusion of REs technologies. For instance, a study by Negro et al (2012), shows that
365 a lack of stable institutions that promote REs, and a poor alignment of these institutions with other
366 sectors and regional/local institutions are key systemic problems; this is also true in the specific case
367 of Ukraine. Therefore, additional attention is needed from policy makers and other system actors that
368 have an interest in accelerating the diffusion of renewable energy. It remains unclear whether the
369 expansion of bioenergy, in particular fuel wood, will be accepted by the wider public and
370 environmentalists, although the promotion of REs is generally supported by many Ukrainians.
371 However, community participation in REs schemes, especially where communities directly share in the
372 benefits, has been shown to improve their acceptance (Rogers et al 2008, Warren and McFayden
373 2010). So, it may be that community-led schemes like the ones highlighted in this paper (Table 3), may
374 not face the same kind of opposition.

375 Finally, if the supply of harvesting residues to private companies were profitable for state forest
376 enterprises, or if private enterprises were given access to forests to collect them themselves, the
377 amount of wood used for energy would increase without necessarily compromising landscape or forest
378 ecology. To initiate such a process and to foster the development of a bioenergy market, political
379 attention should be given to implementation of energy strategies (Balitskiy et al. 2014; Baublys et al.
380 2014; Painuly 2001; Kharlamova et al. 2016).

381 **4.2 Green energy for sustainable development in forest-dependent areas**

382 To maximise the economic benefits of REs in forest-dependent areas, rural development policies
383 need to align with local conditions and opportunities while enhancing the competitiveness of rural
384 areas. Key factors for successfully linking REs to rural development and relevant for the Ukrainian
385 Carpathians are:

- 386 • Energy strategies embedded in the local economic development strategy so that they reflect
387 local potential and needs.
- 388 • Integration of REs within larger supply chains in rural economies, such as agriculture,
389 forestry, traditional manufacturing and green tourism.
- 390 • Subsidies limited in both scope and duration.
- 391 • Use of REs resources appropriate for the specific areas.

- 392 • Focus on relatively mature technologies such as heat from biomass.
- 393 • Establishment of integrated energy systems based on small grids able to support
- 394 manufacturing activities. This includes the recognition that REs compete with other sectors
- 395 for inputs.
- 396 • Assessment of potential projects using investment criteria (vs. short-term subsidies).
- 397 • Ensuring social acceptance by sharing benefits ~~with~~ local communities and engaging them
- 398 in the process (OECD 2012).

399

400 Forests are not just providers of primary resources, but supply a number of other essential ecosystem
401 services, and increasing the timber and fuel wood harvest would require adaptations in forest
402 management. Fostering bioenergy should not need exemption from current requirements for forests
403 to be sustainably managed for multiple goods and services. Woody biomass energy potential must be
404 assessed on Sustainable Forest Management principles, which can be subdivided into: theoretically
405 possible, technically accessible, environmentally safe, economically profitable, and socially
406 conditioned factors (Vasylyshyn 2017).

407 In general, increasing bioenergy production and use in Ukraine brings both important opportunities,
408 as well as significant threats that must be carefully balanced in an integrated and systematic manner
409 while considering trade-offs with ecosystem services (e.g., carbon sequestration or biodiversity). Key
410 advantages and disadvantages are considered below.

411 The following *opportunities* can be envisaged from increased use of forest bioenergy: 1) it is a locally
412 widely available natural and renewable resource; 2) It offers a sustainable way of recycling forestry
413 residues; 3) it directly replaces fossil fuels as an energy source and thus can reduce carbon emissions;
414 4) it provides an additional source of income for local people and industries; 5) it increases Ukraine's
415 energy independence and energy security; 6) It is a storable energy source with multiple uses for heat,
416 gas and electricity; 7) forest biomass can provide ecosystem services (e.g. carbon sequestration and
417 biodiversity).

418 The following *threats* can be identified from increased use of forest bioenergy: 1) extensive forest
419 biomass use could lead to forest overexploitation, if not properly regulated, especially if energy prices
420 rise -; 2) it requires adaptation of the forest management system and processes along the wood
421 production chain; 3) it is low carbon, not carbon neutral, due to emissions from transport and
422 processing; 4) if bioenergy from wood becomes a profitable business, big companies, rather than local
423 communities, could benefit in the first instance; 5) it has environmental impacts, in particular if timber
424 is used for fuel.. 6) poorly regulated forestry can negatively impact ecosystem services (e.g. carbon
425 sequestration and biodiversity).

426 Knowledge co-production activities could help to engage stakeholders in the REs sector (Hewitt et al.
427 2017). Several studies indicate that REs projects can be developed to the advantage of local interests
428 and sustainable rural development, for example, by creating direct jobs (operating and maintaining
429 equipment, for example). Most long-term jobs found all along the supply chain are indirect
430 (construction, manufacturing, or in forestry and agriculture in the case of biomass). Some studies
431 reported innovations (e.g. the development of new products, practices and policies) in rural areas with
432 REs installations (Geletukha 2006; Björnsen Gurung and Seidl 2017; FORZA 2017; Soloviy et al. 2018;
433 Björnsen Gurung et al. 2018; Nijnik et al. 2019). REs projects can generate revenues for farmers or
434 forest owners, but also for land owners or local authorities. It is often stated that communities
435 producing their own energy may become less dependent on the price fluctuations of conventional

436 fuels, which in turn improves living conditions, increases competitiveness, and resolves the problem
437 of energy dependence.

438 Wood certification schemes could offer another promising entry point for the sustainable use of forest
439 biomass. At global level, several certification schemes developed for a range of products and sectors
440 are available for various purposes (e.g. fair-trade, organic agriculture). Forest certification schemes
441 such as the Forest Stewardship Council (FSC) were developed primarily to ensure sustainable forest
442 management (Van Dam et al. 2010). In response to the sustainability concerns in biofuel production,
443 several new certification schemes were developed worldwide. The EU has also proposed that Member
444 States should use the same criteria for the use of solid and gaseous biomass for energy production.
445 However, sustainability requirements do not apply for biomass used for the production of bio-based
446 products and bio-chemicals. A number of initiatives have been launched to develop voluntary
447 sustainability standards for the production and conversion of biomass to bioenergy. These certification
448 schemes include limited environmental, economic and social aspects, while some specific issues are
449 missed, such as indirect effects, food availability and security. The environmental viability of biofuels
450 has been questioned based on concerns over indirect land-use changes that need to be addressed in
451 a certification scheme for bio-based materials in general (Scarlat et al. 2015).

452 However, the majority of stakeholders engaged in our study supported energy production from forest
453 products both in the Ukrainian Carpathians, and in Ukraine as a whole. As Vorobei and Hudz (2017)
454 have observed, in a study of the status of the bioenergy market in nine western regions of Ukraine,
455 communities play an important role in market development. A range of factors, including
456 decentralization, the increase of financial resources in communities, and the need for energy saving,
457 are likely to stimulate demand for bioenergy solutions at the local level. Further, it is expected that the
458 interest of communities in public-private partnership with energy service companies will increase and
459 that communal enterprises will become more significant players in the market leading to a growing
460 biofuel demand. In particular, private companies with transparent public-private partnership
461 mechanisms will benefit from the emerging market. On the other hand, a lack of expert support in the
462 organization of public-private partnership processes in bioenergy might prove to be a deterrent.

463

464 **4.3 Innovative initiatives for green energy transition: lessons learnt**

465 Both the Best Practice Contest and the project “Green Energy Options” focus on both rural and urban
466 communities. Our research aimed at system understanding and social relevance, it was action-oriented
467 from the outset of the project, and specifically designed to help trigger local activities to enhance
468 energy provision, energy security and energy efficiency. Including the vision and experience of people
469 for whom forests really matter, i.e. communities in the rural Carpathians, provided a valuable basis for
470 the establishment and re-adjustment of research priorities.

471 Fuel wood could certainly contribute to the reduction of Ukraine’s dependence on fossil fuels and
472 imported energy. Ukraine already has thousands of private REs installations. Entire villages in the Kiyv,
473 Vinnytsia, Kharkiv, Lviv region have become entirely energy self-sufficient, some of them even selling
474 surplus heat or electricity (Melnyk 2017). However, these initiatives are scattered and not
475 systematically promoted. According to a comparative analysis on energy cooperatives in Eastern
476 Europe (Eichermüller and Habersbrunner 2018), civil society in the Ukraine has been a strong actor in
477 the democratic transition and thus, could also play a determinant role in the development of energy
478 cooperatives and other community energy initiatives. Currently, rapid change is still hampered by the
479 economic crisis.

480 Considering the role of certification as a policy instrument, we suggest that biomass energy production
481 would be much more advanced if forest and woodworking enterprises were motivated through
482 bioenergy products certification. This statement is based in outcomes analysis of the successful
483 implementation of FSC forest certification standards in the Ukrainian forest sector during recent years.
484 Ninety percent of the forests under control of the State Agency for Forest Resources in the Ukrainian
485 Carpathians are certified. However, FSC also was criticized by the recent Earthsight Report (2018), on
486 the basis of its inability to ensure legality in Ukraine. Certification is only likely to be successful, if illegal
487 logging and miss-classification of wood can be controlled. To do this, it would be necessary to collect
488 data on suppliers throughout the supply chain, and analyse both the risk of illegality and measures to
489 mitigate against it, e.g. through developing a due diligence system of wood business companies. These
490 initiatives are likely to be beneficial to REs business development, would promote energy
491 independence of Ukraine, and strengthen the bio-economy as a whole.

492 However, the results of our interviews revealed weaknesses and threats related to the development
493 of such certification schemes. The complexity and cost of the certification procedures are clear
494 obstacles. . Also, the fact that the majority of Ukraine's heating systems uses gas instead of wood,
495 makes certification unattractive. An additional important threat relates to the insecurity of green
496 tariffs. In some European countries (e.g. GB, ES, GR) formerly generous feed-in-tariff schemes have
497 been abolished resulting in a decline in newly installed capacity (e.g. Alonso et al 2016; Karneyeva and
498 Wüstenhagen 2017). In Ukraine as elsewhere, reliable and predictable public policies and incentives
499 are needed to stimulate the transition to renewable energies. In the case of the Carpathians, specific
500 measures are needed for solid fuel boilers. Getting the policy landscape right could trigger an inflow
501 of funds to promote green energy initiatives, reduce CO₂ emissions, and contribute to local economies.

502

503 **5. Conclusions**

504 Domestic renewable energy, in particular bioenergy from forests, has a vital role to play in
505 strengthening Ukraine's sovereignty and energy security at the local scale. Steering the green energy
506 transformation process in the Carpathian mountain region requires sound system understanding and
507 a well-designed procedure allowing communities and individuals to shape their energy futures. In the
508 context of the country's post-Soviet history, this process calls for careful planning, long time-frames
509 and a high degree of flexibility, as citizen involvement and other public participation is almost non-
510 existent.

511 Accordingly, to launch successful REs projects at the local scale requires a sound understanding of the
512 larger European and national political frameworks. Indeed, bioenergy has a key role in the European
513 Union (EU) policy and its implementation at national, regional and local levels calls for the inclusion of
514 stakeholders' opinions to increase social acceptance and to reduce conflicts (Nikodinoska et al. 2015).
515 The harmonization of the environmental policy of Ukraine with EU policies in the framework of
516 Ukraine's association membership in the EU, as well as the geopolitical situation defines the interests
517 in advancing green energy development. The institutional efforts towards an integration with Europe's
518 community energy movement are essential to strengthen communities' "green energy" initiatives.

519 These larger frameworks and policies set the stage for the analysis of local/regional energy systems as
520 a basis for the consecutive design of an economic development strategy, including energy production
521 and consumption. Agreement on a local energy strategy encompassing larger supply chains and
522 linkages to other sectors would be the next logical step, ideally developed through a participatory

523 approach to ensure maximum acceptance. Such analysis includes sound knowledge and information
524 on the required resource base, available potentials and the anticipated impacts of altered
525 management practices and regulatory systems, both in the present and in future.

526 However, clear opportunities for further research can be identified with respect to the potential
527 opportunities arising from ~~benefits of~~ the long-term transformation of energy and the economy at the
528 local level, and the role of education and research institutions in supporting the “green energy
529 transition”.

530 This research addresses a topic of key relevance to Ukraine’s energy transition, the potential for locally
531 led innovation to transform the forest bioenergy sector. Our findings, based on a stakeholder-centred
532 approach, help raise awareness of this topic at local, regional and national scales, thereby increasing
533 knowledge of opportunities and threats for a broad range of policy-makers and other stakeholders. By
534 providing a larger picture of the potential role of fuel wood in the Ukrainian Carpathians from a natural
535 science as well as social science perspective, this research contributes to sound decision-making
536 related to the Ukrainian energy transition. Approaches like the one we have followed in this paper
537 offer good potential to enable communities, local entrepreneurs and policy-makers to include
538 bioenergy, in particular the use of fuel wood, into their local and regional development strategies and
539 portfolios.

540

541 **Acknowledgements**

542 The research was implemented in the framework of the project “Identifying Green Option for the
543 Ukrainian Carpathians”, part of the Swiss-Ukrainian Research Cooperation (2017-2020) supported by
544 the Swiss Secretariat for Research, Education and Innovation (SBFI). The project is implemented in an
545 institutional partnership of the Swiss Federal Research Institute WSL, Ukrainian National Forestry
546 University, the NGO FORZA Agency of sustainable development of the Carpathian region, and the
547 Center for Development and Environment (CDE) of the University of Bern. Richard J. Hewitt gratefully
548 acknowledges funding provided by the Rural Affairs and the Environment Strategic Research Program
549 of the Scottish Government, and the European Commission under the remit of European Union
550 Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Program grant No. 677622, awarded to the project Social
551 Innovation in Marginalized Rural Areas (SIMRA). We would like to acknowledge the contributions and
552 valuable insights gained from the participants of the Best Practices Contest.

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